

MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING APPROACH: ITS EFFECT ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN PRE-CALCULUS

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ABSTRACT

With the new normal that the world is currently facing, education becomes more challenging to face, survive, to continue and many people have suffered. For the continuity of education and for every school to still attain its mission and vision which is to provide quality education to every Filipino learner, the Department of Education implemented the Modular Distance Learning. This study was conducted to examine the effect of Modular Distance Learning Approach to Students Performance in Pre-Calculus, determine the significant difference on students' Performance in Pre-Calculus when grouped according to gender and determine the factors that can affect the student Performance in Pre-Calculus when engaging while engaging in Modular Distance Learning Approach. Described method design was used in the study. One intact class consist of fifty-nine (59) students Grade 11 STEM 1-FRUED who are currently enrolled in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High Department was utilized as the research sample through purposive sampling. Questionnaire checklist was applied in gathering the data. Mean, frequency counts, percentage and t-test for independent sample was used as the statistical tools.

Keywords: modular learning approach, performance, pre-calculus

INTRODUCTION

The performance of the students on the use of the modules can be conducted regularly. While the use of modules for instruction develops independent learning; it is recommended that during the implementation phase of the module, strengths and weaknesses be identified. That is, in lessons/tasks where students did not quite do well, more exercises or activities be developed. The regular, assigned and evaluative tasks may be updated and be reviewed to improve the content of the modules. Emphasis be given to assigned tasks since student output depends on how well these tasks are to be accomplished; to test student knowledge and application of skills, paragraph development, one-on-one questioning of students, questionnaire to measure how well the students has improved his values, among others. It is recommended that teachers conduct relative researches on module preparation to include areas such as the use of rubrics to evaluate the outputs, to include content teachers to validate the inputs on various areas, and to increase the number of participants or respondents.

“Whatever is happening in the country; whatever challenges we are facing, education must continue. Education cannot wait; our learners cannot wait. We continue with the process so we can give hope and continuity, and contribute to the normalization of activities in the country.” –DepEd Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones.

Sabbaha N. et. al, (2024) as cited by Mading F. et al, (2024) Learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within individual’s mind, it is an ability possessed by human being that plays a crucial role in the existence of human life, from the moment a person was brought into this world, the process of learning begins until he or she reaches the stage of late adulthood which means that learning is a continuous process. Jailani, A. et.al, (2024) as cited by Abdulmajid et al., (2024) and Sabbaha N. et. al, (2024) Although the pandemic may have passed by now, its effects are still felt, thus education needs to continue. Indeed, education is the key to success, thus it shouldn't be interrupted, so the government has come up with a way to meet the demands of the learners while allowing the children to continue their education.

With the new normal the world is currently facing, education becomes more challenging to face, survive, to continue and many people have suffered. As uttered by Balla, F.J. (2024) cited by Abdulmajid et al., (2024) In the Philippines, most of the students are facing several challenges, examples are family problems, poverty, the large number of students in each classroom, lack of motivation and low self-confidence, and bullying. Each of these problems has a great impact on the student’s learning process. The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a widespread disruption such as travel restrictions, closure of schools and global economic recession. Suddenly, parents, students and teachers alike were forced to learn a new way of schooling. Face to face engagement of students and teachers within the school has also been suspended yet despite the initial discomfort; the benefits of distance learning go far beyond protection from the virus. For the continuity of education and for every school to still attain its mission and vision which is to provide quality education to every Filipino learner, the Department of Education implemented the Modular Distance Learning.

Modular Distance Learning features individualized instruction that allows learners to use self-learning modules in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever is applicable to the Learner. Learners under Modular Distance Learning can also use other resources such as Learner's materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and other study materials. Usually, teachers will have to deliver appropriate learning materials. However, student can also access these materials by downloading electronic copies through their computer, tablet, or smart phone.

According to Tan and Pagtulon-an (2018) in their study "Students' Mathematics Performance and Self-Efficacy Beliefs in a rich assessment tasks environment", Modules also developed the interest towards mathematical thinking and concepts among learners and helped to achieve good scores in tests rather than the traditional way of teaching. Students performed very well who are taught by some modules rather than those students who are taught by the traditional method.

Modular instruction is one of those teaching approaches where the students have to set themselves active in the learning process. The students utilize their own abilities at their own pace. It differs from the traditional one where conceptual learning of students is kept forth by the teacher instead of just focusing on lecture delivery by the teacher. Students usually face difficulties in the traditional classroom environment. Whereas, the modular approach may be a good alternate to traditional teaching. The student has the responsibility of learning about his attitude and behavior. The teacher's set of instructions kept in the module provide functional student-teacher interaction.

Moreover, Aksan (2020) in her study "Effect of Modular Distance Learning Approach to Academic Performance in Mathematics" the modular distance learning approach must be continuing in face-to-face instruction even the COVID-19 pandemic vanish. Since it proved that this is going to improve the mathematical understanding and helped the students to get higher performance. This is highly recommended to use modules during instructions for students to read advance about the specific topic in Mathematics. Along with the process of Modular Distance Learning Approach, subject matter such as English, Filipino, History, Science and Mathematics may use a textbook, activity sheets and other study materials as reference and guide in understanding a certain topic. This will require a deep understanding of word meaning to see the function and benefits of the said subjects and to understand it effectively.

Aksan (2020) the modular distance learning approach must be continuing in face-to-face instruction even the COVID-19 pandemic vanishes. Since it proved that this is going to improve the mathematical understanding and helped the students to get higher performance. This is highly recommended to use modules during instructions for students to read advance about the specific topic in Mathematics. Teachers will monitor the learners' progress, feedback mechanisms, and guide those who need special attention. They are also needed to be more flexible and even-minded in any situations. Also teachers need to prepare easy type of modules in Mathematics to understand and assess. This module is quite challenging and interesting in the part of students especially in Math subject.

In this research study, the researchers are interested in providing a better

understanding of the relationship between Modular Distance Learning Approach and Students' Performance in Pre-Calculus and see if the learner's need was met by the program. With that, the researchers will come across in finding answer to the questions formulated in the Statement of the Problem.

Thus, the purpose of this study is to examine the effect of modular distance learning approach in Pre-Calculus to the academic performance of students. To give significant plan to the educators to improve the teaching-learning process even this pandemic vanished and how it can be implemented effectively so the teachers embrace its use.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study aimed to determine the effects of Modular Distance Learning Approach to students' Performance in Pre-Calculus in particular this study attempt to answer the following questions:

1. What is the perceive effect of Modular Distance Learning Approach to Students' Performance in Pre-Calculus?
2. Is there a significant difference on students' Performance in Pre-Calculus when grouped according to gender?
3. What are the factors that can affect the Students' Performance in Pre-Calculus while engaging in Modular Distance Learning Approach?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu specifically in the Senior High School Department located at Capitol Hills, Patikul, Sulu.

Sampling Method

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani A. et al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. Moreover, the selected respondents consist of 59 students. (10) Male and Fifteen (49) Female.

Research Instrument

The researchers used survey questionnaire checklist in collecting the data. The questionnaires were consisting of three parts: (1) Demographic Profile; (2) Questionnaire checklist for the statement on the effect of Modular Distance Learning Approach toward students' performance in Pre-Calculus; (3) Questionnaire checklist for the statement on the factors that can affect the students' performance in Pre-Calculus while engaging in Modular

Distance Learning Approach?”

SCALE	INTERVAL	DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENCE
1	1.0-1.75	STRONGLY DISAGREE
2	1.75-2.5	DISAGREE
3	2.51-3.25	AGREE
4	3.26-4.0	STRONGLY AGREE

Legend: 3.26-4.0 (Strongly Agree); 2.51-3.25 (Agree); 1.75-2.5 (Strongly Agree); 1.0-1.75 (Strongly Disagree)

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools that the researchers used were the following:

Weighted Mean for the statement of the problem “What is the perceived effect of Modular Distance Learning Approach to Students Academic Performance in Pre-Calculus?”

t-test for independent sample for the statement “Is there significant difference on students’ performance when grouped according to gender”. The independent sample t-test compares the mean of two independent groups in order to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the associated population means are significantly different.

Frequency counts and percentage in answering the statement: “What are the factors that can affect the students’ performance in Pre-Calculus while Engaging in Modular Distance Learning Approach?”

Ranking for the statement: “What is the perceived effect of Modular Distance Learning Approach to Students Academic Performance in Pre-Calculus?” and “What are the factors that can affect the students’ performance in Pre-Calculus while Engaging in Modular Distance Learning Approach?”

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the effect of Modular Distance Learning Approach to Students’ Performance in Pre-Calculus. The participant of this study is delimited to the selected respondents consist of 59 students. (10) Male and Fifteen (49) Female coming from Mindanao State University-Sulu, Senior High School Department located at Capitol Hills, Patikul, Sulu.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents, analyzes and interprets the data of the study in relation to the research problems.

Table 4.1 Weighted Mean, Description and Ranking for The Perceived Effects of Modular Distance Learning to Student's Performance in Pre-Calculus

STATEMENT	MEAN	Description	RANK
1. Requires self-determination and effort to learn the topic.	3.36	STRONGLY AGREE	1 ST
2. Allow students read lectures from different sources.	3.19	AGREE	2 ND
3. Is stressful to understand alone.	3.09	AGREE	3 RD
4. Saves time to answer the activities before deadline.	3.02	AGREE	4 TH
5. Gives students the possibility to get good grades in Pre-Calculus.	3.0	AGREE	5 TH
6. Activates students' critical thinking in solving problems.	2.98	AGREE	6 TH
7. Helps student manage their time in studying the lectures and answering the activities.	2.83	AGREE	7 TH
8. Give students a hard time in answering activities.	2.80	AGREE	8 TH
9. Can boost self-esteem in solving the problems.	2.78	AGREE	9 TH
10. Made students rely on their friends, parents and relatives in answering activities.	2.74	AGREE	10 TH
11. Made students struggle in seeking advice and explanations from the subject teacher.	2.71	AGREE	11 TH
12. Students' learning has no improvement.	2.71	AGREE	
13. Give students the chance to cheat.	2.68	AGREE	12 TH
14. Give students the chance to cheat.	2.68	AGREE	13 TH
15. Pressure students in solving problems.	2.56	AGREE	14 TH
16. Made Students slack-off instead of studying the lectures.	2.33	DISAGREE	15 TH

17. Doesn't allow students sleep on time.	2.31	DISAGREE	16 TH
18. Made students Lazy and Uninterested.	2.28	AGREE	17 TH
19. Doesn't allow students understand the topic accurately with his/her own.	2.25	DISAGREE	18 TH
20. Is better than traditional face-to-face Instruction.	2.20	DISAGREE	19 TH
GRAND MEAN	2.72	AGREE	

Legend: 3.26-4.0 (Strongly Agree); 2.51-3.25 (Agree); 1.75-2.5 (Disagree); 1.0-1.75 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 4.1 presents the weighted mean of the statements who answered Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree for the effects of Modular Distance Learning Approach to the respondents. The total weighted mean was 2.72 which mean that the descriptive equivalent is Agree.

The Respondents answered “strongly Agree” with a weighted mean of 3.36 and ranked first on the statement “It requires self-determination and effort to learn the topic.” and it further implies that it has a very strong effect.

On the other hand, majority of the respondents agreed on the statements regarding the effects of Modular Distance Learning Approach towards them namely; Allow students read lectures from different sources; Can boost self-esteem in solving the problems; Saves time to answer the activities before deadline; Give students a hard time in answering activities; Helps student manage their time in studying the lectures and answering the activities; Activates students’ critical thinking in solving problems; Gives students the possibility to get good grades in Pre-Calculus; Pressure students in solving problems; Students’ learning has no improvement; Made students struggle in seeking advice and explanations from the subject teacher; Is stressful to understand alone; Give students the chance to cheat; Made students rely on their friends, parents and relatives in answering activities; Made students Lazy and Uninterested; Provides opportunity to earn money while studying. Moreover, these statements have strong effect.

There are also respondents who disagreed on the statements namely; it doesn’t allow students sleep on time, doesn’t allow students understand the topic accurately with his/her own, is better than traditional face-to-face Instruction, and it made Students slack-off instead of studying the lectures. And it further implies that these statements don’t have an effect on their academic performance.

Table 4.2 Level of Academic Performance in Pre-Calculus of the Grade 11 Stem 1 Freud

MEAN	Std. Deviation	Description
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MALE	86	5.637178	Very Satisfactory
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FEMALE	90.08163	4.152493	Outstanding
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Rating obtained	88.04	4.89	Very Satisfactory
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Legend: 90-100(Outstanding); 85-89(Very Satisfactory); 80-84(Satisfactory); 75-79(Fairly Satisfactory); 75 below (Did Not Meet Expectation)

Table 4.2 presents the computed weighted Mean, standard deviation and the description. As shown in the table, the computed grades of the male which results as the weighted mean was 86 with a standard deviation of 5.64 and base from DepEd grading system it was very satisfactory. On the other hand, the computed grades of the female were 90.08 which is their weighted mean with a standard deviation of 4.15 and resulted as outstanding. Thus, the rating obtained for both Male and Female was very satisfactory. The weighted mean was 88.04 and a standard deviation of 4.89.

Cumulative Grades in Pre-Calculus of the Randomly Selected 20 Students of The Grade 11 Stem 1 Freud

	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
75-79 (Fairly Satisfactory)	1	10	0	0
80-84 (Satisfactory)	4	40	0	0
85-89(Very Satisfactory)	1	10	2	20
90-100 (Outstanding)	4	40	8	80
Total	10	100	10	100

The above table shows the cumulative grades in Pre-calculus of the randomly selected male and female students of Grade 11 Stem-1 Freud. The Frequency and percentage of the obtained grades are grouped into two: Male and Female.

In the Male Group which is in the second column of the top row, only one student got grades under Fairly Satisfactory which is 10% of the population of the Male Group, four student got grades under Satisfactory (40% of the population of the Male Group), 1 student got grade under Very Satisfactory (10% of the population of the Male Group), and four students got grades under Outstanding (40% of the population of the Male Group).

Moving on to the Female Group which is in the 3rd column of the top row, no one got grades for both under Fairly Satisfactory (0% of population of the Female Group), two student got grades under Very Satisfactory (20% of the Population of the Female Group), and Lastly, 8 student got grades under Outstanding (80% of the population of the Female Group).

Table 4.2 T-Test Result on the Academic Performance When Grouped According to Gender

Gender	Population (N)	Mean	SD	Df	α	t-value	Critical value	Decision
MALE	10	86	5.3479	18	0.05	3.08	1.734	Reject Ho
FEMALE	10	92	3.04777					

The table 4.2 above shows the solution of t-test on the academic performance of students when group according to Gender. The population of the selected respondents of this study was unbalanced when grouped according to Gender containing only 10 Male students and 49 Female students. To make the population balance, the researcher made a lottery to choose the other 10 students from the Female Group and came up with the total population (N) of 20 students, ten (10) Male and Ten (10) Female to use in the t-test.

In the Male Group which is in the 1st column of the second row, the average mean of the obtained Grade is 86 with a standard deviation of 5.3479 and the Female Group, average mean of the obtained Grade is 92 with a standard deviation of 3.04777.

With the degree of freedom of 18 and level of significance at 0.05, the obtained critical value is 1.734. Since the obtained 1.734 critical value is lower than the 3.08 t-value, the decision is Reject Ho and Accept the H_A. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the performances of students when grouped according to Gender. It further implies that Female advanced more than male in terms of performance in pre-calculus.

Table 4.3 Mean, Description and Ranked of the Factors That Can Affect the Academic Performance of the Grade 11 Stem-1 Freud While They Are Engaging in A Modular Distance Learning Approach.

FACTORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTON	RANK
1. Lack of experiences in solving problems related to Pre-Calculus.	3.02	AGREE	1 st
2. Social Media Engagement.	2.95	AGREE	2 nd
3. Poor Internet connection.	2.93	AGREE	3 rd
4. Lack of sleep.	2.88	AGREE	4 th
5. Doesn't have guidance from parents regarding the activities.	2.80	AGREE	5 th
6. Lack of supplementary reading materials.	2.76	AGREE	6 th
7. Lack of understanding of basic operations in Mathematics. 8. Doesn't have enough time in answering activities because of Household chores.	2.75	AGREE	7 th

9. Financial problem. 10. Using free time to watch movies, read comics, and plays online games.	2.69	AGREE	8th
11. Modules are not understandable in terms of explanation.	2.68	AGREE	9th
12. Lack of Mobile Phone/Personal Computer.	2.47	DISAGREE	10th
13. Module is costly.	2.42	DISAGREE	11th
14. Lack of interest to Learn.	2.39	AGREE	12th
15. Lack of guidance about the topic from subject teacher.	1.92	DISAGREE	13th
TOTAL MEAN	2.31	AGREE	

The table 2.1 presents the factors that can affect the academic performance of the Grade 11 stem-1 Freud while engaging in a modular distance learning approach in Pre-calculus. As shown in the table, 12 given statements were resulted as Agree and 3 statements disagree by the respondents. The respondents have agreed on the statements namely; Modules are not understandable in terms of explanation, Lack of experiences in solving problems related to Pre-Calculus, Lack of interest to Learn, Poor Internet connection, Lack of understanding of basic operations in Mathematics, Financial problem, Lack of sleep, Social Media Engagement, Lack of supplementary reading materials, Using free time to watch Movies, read comics and play online games, Doesn't have guidance from parents regarding the activities and Doesn't have enough time in answering activities because of Household chores. Moreover, these statements have strong effect. On the otherhand, there are 3 statements that was disagree by the respondents namely; Lack of guidance about the topic from subject teacher, Lack of Mobile Phone/Personal Computer and Module is costly. And it further implies that these statements don't have an effect on their academic performance.

FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION, PERCENTAGES AND RANK OF THE FACTORS WHILE ENGAGING IN A MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING APPROACH

As shown in table 2.2, 80% of the population which ranked first has agreed on the factors namely; Modules are not understandable in terms of explanation, Lack of experiences in solving problems related to Pre-Calculus, Lack of interest to Learn, Poor Internet connection, Lack of understanding of basic operations in Mathematics, Financial problem, Lack of sleep, Social Media Engagement, Lack of supplementary reading materials, using free time to watch movie, read comics and play online games, Doesn't have guidance from parents regarding the activities and Doesn't have enough time in answering activities because of Household chores. It further implies that these statements have strong effect to the students' academic performance in Pre-Calculus. And the remaining 20% of the

population that ranked second have disagreed on the statements; Lack of guidance about the topic from subject teacher, Lack of Mobile Phone/Personal Computer and Module is costly. Moreover, these factors don't have an effect to the students' academic performance in Pre-Calculus.

DESCRIPTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	RANK
STRONGLY AGREE	0	0%	3 rd
AGREE	12	80%	1 st
DISAGREE	3	20%	2 nd
STRONGLY DISAGREE	0	0%	3 rd
TOTAL	15	100%	

Conclusions

In this study, the academic performance of the Grade 11 Stem-1 FREUD in Pre-calculus achieved very satisfactory in school year 2020-2021 while engaging in a Modular Distance Learning Approach. The study revealed the positive effects of Modular Distance Learning Approach amidst COVID-19 Pandemic. These are the top five effects, "Modular Distance Learning Approach requires self-determination and effort to learn the topic. It allows students to read lectures from different sources. It is stressful to understand alone. It saves time to answer the activities before deadline. And lastly, it gives students the possibility to get good grades in Pre-Calculus."

The null hypothesis was rejected if there is no significant difference on the academic performance when grouped according to gender and accept the alternative hypothesis. The study revealed that there is a significant difference on the academic performance when grouped according to gender. Hence, there are factors that could affect the academic performance while engaging in a Modular Distance Learning Approach. These are the top five factors, "Lack of experiences in solving problems related to Pre-Calculus; Social Media Engagement; Poor Internet connection; Lack of sleep; and lastly, it doesn't have guidance from parents regarding the activities."

Therefore, the researchers concluded that there are positive effects of Modular Distance Learning Approach to the Grade 11 Stem 1-FREUD in Pre-calculus. This means that this approach requires self-determination and effort to learn the topic. And also, this study reveals the factors that could affect the academic performance while engaging in a Modular Distance Learning Approach. This means that the quality of performance in getting high, average or low grades did not depend on their perceptions about the effects but the factors could affect their academic performance. And the researchers also concluded that this approach allow students read lectures from different sources; it is stressful to understand alone and gives students the possibility to get good grades in Pre-Calculus.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the researchers recommended the following:

1. The Modular Distance Learning Approach requires self-determination and effort to learn the topic amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. Teachers should monitor the learners' progress, feedback mechanism, and guide those who need special attention. This approach allows the students read lectures from different sources and saves time to answer the activities before deadline. On the other hand, it made the students struggle in seeking advice and explanations from the subject teacher and the students becomes lazy and uninterested. Lastly, it is stressful to understand alone that made the students rely on their friends, parents and relatives in answering activities.
2. Parents and guardians should guide their children at home by means of helping them learn the things that are not visible for them and at least be by their side to cheer them up, motivate and study hard.
3. Math Teacher should adopt policy that could motivate the learners to learn the subject matter and make the instructional materials more interesting that could arouse the curiosity and interest of the students. The module must be clear and have supporting documents like videos for additional explanation aside from the hard copy so that the students could really learn very well and will satisfy their eagerness to learn.
4. Administration should give attention in preparing the modules to be given to learners that are understandable in terms of explanation that can boost self-esteem in solving the problems; activates students' critical thinking in solving problems; and gives students the possibility to get good performance in Pre-calculus; enhance the experiences in solving problems related to pre-calculus. The School Director or the Principal should conduct trainings, workshops, and seminars to the teacher to improve themselves in the use of Modular approach and effective teaching in Pre-calculus. Thus, they should also create a policy in giving supplementary reading materials and provide an opportunity to the students to be a scholar.
5. School Administrator should facilitate the teachers and monitor the academic performance of the students in the midst of pandemic and most specially to take care of the mental health of the students. The school administrator should conduct a seminar or conference to the Math Teachers to address and to enhance the students' intellectual comprehension.
6. For future researchers they should be conducting incorporating other variables not investigated in this study and another related study in other schools in SULU.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For the compliance of this study, the researchers assure ethical standards were followed. In gathering the data needed, the first step was validating the research questionnaire checklist. Three (3) panels of experts from the field were tapped to validate the questions. After which, the researchers seek a letter of approval from the Director of MSU-Sulu Senior High School Department to conduct the survey legally. While waiting for the approval, researchers provide an exact copy of questionnaire needed for the survey. When letter of approval was granted, survey was conducted right away. Upon the survey, the researchers sought help in administering the questionnaire from the adviser of the respondents. After which, the researchers collected the answered questionnaire, tally, present, analyze and interpret the result. The researchers hereby declare that an informed consent was obtained. In accumulation, the researchers assure that the information gathered from respondents are kept intact and confidential.

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